

A new fractal classification and a novel conjecture based on dimension continuity

Abstract

This paper proposes a new way to classify fractals based on varying of their iteration rules.

1. Static fractals: if the rules never change.
2. Dynamic fractals.

And dynamic fractals can be classified as 2.1 dynamic structure fractals (the varying of iterations have certain structures or patterns, like dynamic linear structure fractals, dynamic non-linear structure fractals), and 2.2 dynamic random fractals (some randomness will be introduced into the variation of iteration, like fractals with static structure and randomness, fractals with linear structure and randomness, fractals with non-linear structure and randomness).

It also builds a full mathematical model and analysis which introduces the X-fractal basis from the perspective of measure, direction, position, and quantity, based on this classification.

Which offer a more clear and intuitive classification, providing a new mathematic framework to analysis fractals.

This paper also discuss the Hausdorff dimension and the measure, try to propose a new way to describe the dimension continuity and try to reveal the nature of the continuity and the connections to the symmetry of iterating structures of fractals with a more general concept of entropy symmetry.

Keywords

- Hausdorff Dimension, Hausdorff Measure, Gauge Measure, Brownian Motion Trajectory, Classification, Dimension Continuity, Dimension Basis, X-fractal Basis, Tree Fractal, Randomness, Symmetry, Entropy Symmetry.

Introduction

Current Major Classifications

Now for fractals, there are many ways to classify them. Here are several major classifications as below.

Classification By Self-Similarity Structure:

- i. Exact Self-Similarity Fractals: Exact the same structure at any scale, usually generated by math functions. Most strict ideal fractal. (e.g., Koch snowflake, Sierpinski triangle)
- ii. Quasi-Self-Similarity Fractals: Quiet similar structure at any scale, but not identical, more close to natural objects. (e.g., the Mandelbrot set, Newton fractal)
- iii. Statistical Self-Similarity Fractals: The Statistical characters on each scale is similar, like distribution probability, average of roughness of each scale are similar, Most natural fractals belong to this type. (e.g., coastlines, mountain ranges, clouds, network of rivers)
- iv. Multi-fractals: With more than one fractal dimension or scaling rule. (e.g., turbulence in fluids, the distribution of earthquakes, stock market fluctuations in finance, and so on)

Classification By Method of Generation:

- i. Geometric Fractals: Generated by repeating some geometric transformation, with parts being scaled-down copies of the whole. (e.g., fern leaves, Sierpinski triangle, fractal tree)
- ii. Algebraic Fractals: Generated by applying non-linear iterated maps to an arbitrarily small section, often generate fractals with boundaries possessing infinite complexity and rich artistic appeal. (e.g., Julia Set, Mandelbrot set)
- iii. Random Fractals: Introducing some randomness to iteration rules to model natural phenomena. (e.g., fractal terrain, simulated flame, Brownian motion trajectory)

Classification By Spatial Characteristics:

- i. Surface Fractals: The fractal body is dense (with no internal pores), focus on complex, ragged surfaces. (e.g. Rough engineering surfaces, fractured rock surfaces, and porous solids that adsorb gases (such as activated carbon))
- ii. Mass Fractals: The skeleton or mass of a fractal object possesses a fractal structure, with pores of varying scales distributed throughout its interior, describe the distribution of mass through a space. (e.g., Polymer gel, smoke dust aggregation particles, porous soil aggregates)
- iii. Disconnected Fractals: A fractal is composed of a series of discontinuous, isolated points, topologically disconnected components. (e.g. Cantor Set)

Other Classifications:

- i. Self-Affine Fractals: Anisotropic scaling (with different scaling ratios in different directions) is generated by affine transformation, using different scaling parameters in different coordinate directions. (e.g., Mountainous terrain, coastlines, rock/material fracture surfaces, chaotic systems, earthquake sequences, financial markets, and random fractal terrain generation)
- ii. Invariant Fractals: Formed with non-linear transformations, whose key characteristic is to locally preserve angles, but it can also include bending and twisting, resulting in different shapes at different scales. (e.g., Limit sets of Kleinian groups acting on the complex plane, and critical phenomena in statistical physics: certain two-dimensional critical systems (such as the Ising model))
- iii. fractals based on dimensions: Strict fractals and non-strict fractals. For Strict fractals: The Hausdorff dimension is strictly greater than its topological dimension (such as Cantor set, Koch snowflake). For non-strict fractals: Although it exhibits fractal characteristics, its dimension is precisely an integer (e.g., the trajectory of Brownian motion can have a dimension of 2 under certain conditions)

Tools to analysis fractals

Fractal's measure and its dimension

- Similarity Dimension

For the simplest cases of fractals:

We could calculate the dimension d from the formula below:

$$d = \frac{\log(N)}{\log(1/r)}$$

N means the number of smaller copies the object is divided.

r is the scaling factor, which is also the ratio of new copy to original.

For example: in Koch curve, the N is 4, the original line turns to be 4 copies, and r is 1/3, each copy is 1/3 ratio of the original length.

- Things become a bit difficult, when introduced different scaling ratios, like a tree fractal with 2 ratios. So here is Moran Equation:

$$\sum_{i=1}^N (r_i)^d = 1$$

Exceptions: when in a fractal tree consist of lines in a 2D space, if $r_1 = 0.8$, $r_2 = 0.85$, then the $d > 3$, which is weird and intuition contradicting, that's because we don't take overlap into consideration.

- To include the overlap exception, the Minkowski dimension or also called Box-Counting dimension came.

$$d = \lim_{r \rightarrow 0} \left(\frac{\log(N(r))}{\log(1/r)} \right)$$

r is the length of this tiny box.

N is the number of boxes which needed to cover the whole fractal.

Exceptions: when in some extreme cases, that it's not accurate to use all the same box to cover the whole fractal, because in some cases, some part of the fractal which consist with lines previously might turn to be tiny dust points, so that's why the more general form of Hausdorff dimension is introduced, to expand the categories of this tiny box, to cover more kinds of situations.

- To analysis more general fractals, a general Hausdorff measure and Hausdorff dimension were introduced.

Definition of Hausdorff measure and Hausdorff dimension

$$H^s = \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} |U_i|^s$$

$U_i \in \{U_j\}$, $\{U_j\}$ is a countable set of Δ_{cover} , with its diameters at most length with δ .

U_i won't cover each other, the whole fractal will be covered with infinity U_i .

s means s dimension.

H^s means the measure of the fractal under s dimension.

There do exist d which is a critical point and boundary value, that will make:

$$s < d \rightarrow H^s = 0$$

$$s > d \rightarrow H^s = \infty$$

So d is the dimension of this fractal.

Actually, it stays the same intuition with the measure of normal objects, like for dimension 1, $H = \sum(r^1)$; for dimension 2, measure is area, $H = \sum(r^2)$, for dimension 3, measure is volume, $H = \sum(r^3)$; so for dimension d , $H^d = \sum(r^d)$.

To get d , we'll assume $H^d = C$ While C stays constant, which is a subtle conjecture proved by Besicovitch (todo :double check).

The question if only exist one d for the boundary case, brings the concept of Multifractals, a set of dimensions do exist in the same object, like turbulence.

- For some special cases which H^s will always stay 0 or ∞ , expose the Hausdorff measure is limited. That's where Gauge Measures introduced.

Here's the formula of Gauge measures:

$$H^s = \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} h(U_i)$$

The $h(U_i)$ can be $|U_i|^s$ when H^s can be positive finite.

For example, the Brownian Path, when applying the Hausdorff measure, $s = 2$, $H^s = 0$, to refine this measure, so Gauge measure introduce the patch :

$$h(r) = r^2 * \log(1/r) * \log * \log * \log(1/r),$$

$$H^s = N * h(r) = C.$$

There still have exceptions to fractals that you can't find a proper $h(r, s)$ that will make the H^s positive finite. Like Davies' Exceptional Sets, Generic Compact Sets, Non-Minkowski Measurable Fractals and so on.

The exceptions to Gauge measure lead to Multifractal Spectrum, Packing Measure, potential theory.

Above all, We can tell that Hausdorff dimension is a way to describe the dimension continuity of fractals from the perspective of meaningful measure, and Gauge measure is a great patch. Somehow still lack of some more natural and intuitive principles or theories behind it to prove why some object consisted of lines can reach the dimension 2 for some cases. And why can't it break the dimension limits of 2 for another cases. And That's one of the major reason why the author of this paper is trying to provide a new angle to reveal the dimension and its continuity with a short life span ant and symmetry based on a new classification of fractals below.

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Key view2:

Based on dimension continuity and fractal, a new conjecture is proposed that there might exist some basic iteration rules which expand the dimension2. One static rule might just like one basic vector or basic frequency. Enough rules, or enough frequent basis will be able to expand the dimension2, will reach the dimension2, just like the random fractal based on curve.

Key view3:

There might exist a set of basic rules which like Fourier basis, which can explain or real the dimension continuity.

I called it X-Fourier dimension basis.

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Major Contributions:

- i: This paper provides a new classification of fractals and the related mathematical model, which offers a more clear and intuitive way to study fractals.
- ii: We also gave a detailed and full analysis to such classification and the model from the perspective of measure, direction, position, quantity, which create a systematical and new method for fractals, and also provide a more clear analysis especially for some mixed system consisted of strict fractals and non-fractals.
- iii: In this paper, We try to reveal the nature of dimension and its continuity from the angle of a dimension ant with pretty short life span, that gives a vivid and profound view to check the deep nature behind the dimension and its continuity.
- iv: We also propose the conjectures that the dimension will strongly be connected to the symmetry of basic structure and iteration structure, and introduce the concept of entropy symmetry for more general cases, which give a more intuitive and simple tool to analysis some complicated fractals, especially for some fully entropy symmetrical cases.

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Core

Fractal Classification

Static Fractal

- Definition: the iteration rules of fractal doesn't change. The structures are identical for each scale.
- Map to existed classification: Exact Self-Similarity Fractals.
- Examples: Koch snowflake, Sierpinski triangle.

Dynamic Fractal

- Definition: the iteration rules of fractal are varying and dynamic. The structures are different for each scale.
- SubClassification: it can be divided into two categories: dynamic structure fractal and dynamic random fractal.

Dynamic structure fractal

- Definition: The varying of iteration rules or structures of each scale in fractals can be concluded as certain patterns, characteristics. Which means even it's different for each scale, but do exist some common patterns or features in each scale.
- SubClassification: It can be divided into two different classifications: Dynamic linear structure fractal, Dynamic non-linear structure fractal.

A: Dynamic Linear structure fractal:

- Definition: The Variation of iterations rules are linear in fractals.
- Map to existed classifications: Geometric Fractals.
- Examples: fern leaves, fractal tree.

B1. Dynamic Non-Linear structure fractal:

- Definition: The Variation of iterations rules are non-linear in fractals.
- Map to existed classifications: Algebraic Fractals, Quasi-Self-Similarity Fractals(Major part).
- Examples: Julia Set, Mandelbrot set. Newton fractal.

B2. Dynamic Non-Linear anisotropy fractals:

- Definition: There are different patterns in the varying of iteration rules for different direction in fractals.
- Map to existed classifications: Some of Self-Affine Fractals
- Examples:

Dynamic random fractal

- Definition: Introduce randomness into the iteration rules or the varying of structures on each scale.
- Map to existed classifications: Statistical Self-Similarity Fractals; Random Fractals; Self-Affine Fractals; Surface Fractals; Massive Fractals; Disconnected Fractals
- Examples: coastlines, mountain ranges, clouds, network of rivers, fractal terrain, simulated flame, Brownian motion trajectory, Mountainous terrain, coastlines, rock/material fracture surfaces, chaotic systems, earthquake sequences, financial markets, and random fractal terrain generation; smoke dust aggregation particles, porous soil aggregates.
- SubClassifications: static structure with random fractal; linear structure with random fractal; Non-linear structure with random fractal.

A. Fractals With Static Structure And Randomness

- Definition : The major part of varying in iteration rules or structure of fractals are static or fixed, but with some randomness introduced.
- Examples:

B. Fractals With Linear Structure And Randomness

- Definition: The major part of varying in iteration rules or structure of fractals are linear, but with randomness introduced.
- Map to existed classifications:
- Examples:

C1. Fractals With Non-linear Structure And Randomness

- Definition: The major variation of iteration rules of fractal are non-linear, and with randomness being introduced.
- Map to existed classifications:
- Examples:

C2. Fractals With Non-Linear Anisotropy And Randomness

- Definition: There are different patterns in the varying of iteration rules for different direction in fractals, and with some randomness in the varying of iteration rules.
- Map to existed classifications: Self-Affine Fractals(todo check)
- Examples: Mountainous terrain, coastlines, rock/material fracture surfaces, chaotic systems, earthquake sequences, financial markets, and random fractal terrain generation.
D total random fractal??

Core Framework**Mathematic Model:**

Symbol Description:

s_i means the i-th scale of fractals.

XP means the patterns of fractals from perspective of measure(length, area, volume), direction, position, quantity.

R_i means the randomness introduced on i-th scale.

V or V_i means the x-fractal basis.

XF are operators that show the structure with a more clear angle.

- Static fractals:

$$XP(s_i) = V * XP(s_{i-1}) \quad (1.1)$$

$$XF(s_i) = \sum_{j=1}^i XF(V_j) + XF(s_0) \quad (2.1)$$

For static fractals, the V and V_j are Fixed.

- Dynamic Linear Structure fractals:

$$XP(s_i) = V_i * XP(s_{i-1}) \quad (1.2)$$

$$XF(s_i) = \sum_{j=1}^i XF(V_j) + XF(s_0) \quad (2.2)$$

For Dynamic Linear Structure fractals, V_i has some sort of linear relationship with scale i , under certain operation.

- Dynamic Non_Linear Structure fractals:

Simple One:

$$XP(s_i) = V_i * XP(s_{i-1}) \quad (1.31)$$

$$XF(s_i) = \sum_{j=1}^i NF(XF(V_j)) + XF(s_0) \quad (2.31)$$

For such fractals, V_i has some sort of nonlinear relationship with scale i .

Complex One:

$$XP(s_i) = NFunc(V_{i0} * XP_{j0}, V_{i1} * XP_{j1}, V_{i2} * XP_{j2}, ..) \quad (1.32)$$

j_0, j_1, j_2, \dots could be limited combination of integers.

Which means the pattern on i -th scale is not only determined by $i-1$ scale, but could be some sort of combination of certain patterns of several scales.

- Static fractals With randomness:

$$XP(s_i) = V * R_i * XP(s_{i-1}) \quad (1.4)$$

$$XF(s_i) = \sum_{j=1}^i XF(V_j) + XF(s_0) + R' \quad (2.4)$$

V is Fixed.

For Static fractals With randomness, R_i means the randomness introduced on i -th scale.

- Fractals With Linear Structure And Randomness:

$$XP(s_i) = V_i * R_i * XP(s_{i-1}) \quad (1.5)$$

$$XF(s_i) = \sum_{j=1}^i XF(V_j) + XF(s_0) + R' \quad (2.5)$$

For such fractals, V_i has some sort of linear relationship with scale i , under certain operation.

R_i means the randomness introduced on i -th scale.

- Fractals With Non-linear Structure And Randomness:

Simple One:

$$XP(s_i) = V_i * R_i * XP(s_{i-1}) \quad (1.61)$$

V_i is a nonlinear function of i -th scale.

R_i means the randomness introduced on i -th scale.

Complex One:

$$XP(s_i) = NFunc(R_i, V_{i0} * XP_{j0}, V_{i1} * XP_{j1}, V_{i2} * XP_{j2}, ..) \quad (1.62)$$

j_0, j_1, j_2, \dots could be limited combination of integers.

Which means the pattern on i -th scale not only be determined by $i-1$ scale, but could be some sort of combination of certain patterns of several scales.

Notice: s_i, s_j : means the i th, j th scale; R : means randomness; $XP(s_i)$ means the pattern of current fractal on i th scale.

Key Points:

Dimension continuity behind fractal

- What's the dimension of a space.

For every point p_i of the space, there do exist a basis set $B \{b_j\}$ that could describe the point, which means p_i are linear combinations of $B: P = B * A$. And inversely, for every linear combination of B all belong to the space. And the number of basis in B is the dimension of the space, which means:

$$d_{space} = Len(B) \quad (3.0)$$

Examples like 1D space, 2D space, 3D space.

- What's the dimension of an object.
- For normal objects:

There is a set of points P which belong to this object, For each P, there do exist a pretty close area on the object that is small enough, I called it $\Delta(S)$, for each point P' in this $\Delta(S)$ area, it can be expressed as:

$$P' = P + r * B_p * A' / \|A'\| \tag{4.0}$$

r_s means the radius of $\Delta(S)$

r means a smaller enough value, usually in the range of 0 and radius of $\Delta(S)$: $0 \leq r \leq r_s$.

B_p is a set of orthonormal basis.

In which, if we set P as original, then P' means the linear combination of basis in B_p . And the number of basis in B_p means the dimension of the small area in this object.

A' means Vectors in the space of B_p , $A' / \|A'\|$ means directions in the space of B_p , $B_p * A'$ means the linear combination of B_p .

And For the object dimension:

$$d_{normobj} = \text{MFunc}(\text{Len}(B_p)) \tag{5.0}$$

$d_{normobj}$ means the dimension of normal object.

Len means the number of basis in B_p .

MFunc can be Max or Min or Average or other operators.

And especially For normal objects, for the interior points of an object, for such smaller enough area $\Delta(S)$, every possible r length linear combination of B_p will in $\Delta(S)$, which means A' could be consisted of any numbers, and r_s can be any number in the range of $[0, r_s]$, totally covered this area.

PS: for some discontinuous points P or boundaries, the smaller enough area $\Delta(S)$ could be half, part, one-way, r will be zero on certain directions, that means lacking of part directions.

Examples like line, curve, surface, box, and any other objects like those. For each points in an object like those, the $\text{Len}(B_p) = C$, will stay the same, C is fixed and constant, such as 1D objects, lines and curves: $\text{Len}(B_p) = 1$; 2D objects, for planes and usual surface: $\text{Len}(B_p) = 2$; for box, solid sphere, eclipse, cylinder and others like those 3D objects, $\text{Len}(B_p) = 3$.

- For fractals:

The situation becomes a bit different.

First, the $\text{Len}(B_p)$ will not always stay the same, for points in a fractal.

Second, even for some part of interior points of a fractal, r can't just be a random number in $[0, r_s]$, and it won't stay 0 like boundary or discontinue situations, there are holes existed. And I'll describe it and compare it with dimension of normal objects from the perspective of a dimension ant with pretty short life-span so that it can never get out of the area $\Delta(S)$.

- The dimension ant for interior points of a plane below

- The dimension ant for boundary points of a plane below

- The dimension ant for discontinuous points on a curve below

i: For the three images above, they describe the points of interior, boundary, discontinue dimension situation from the perspective of the short-life span ant which started from P .

ii: The blue arrows means the basis vectors in $\{B_p\}$.

iii: green arrows means some possible directions that this ant can go.

iv: For straight lines or planes, the $\{B_p\}$ will stay fixed for each $\Delta(S)$, but for curve lines or curve surfaces, it won't. In curve lines or curve surfaces, the $b_i \in \{B_p\}$ might vary for each point P and its $\Delta(S)$, Although that, the $\text{Len}(B_p)$ will stay the same.

- The dimension ant for fractals like tree fractal or Koch snow below

i: deep blue areas mean barrier area for this ant. For some points of a fractal, the ant still get many directions to go like those green paths show, but with many deep blue areas, once falls in those areas, then it dies.

ii: The green paths in the circle are the paths that this ant can survive.

iii: For normal objects, if the area $\Delta(S)$ is getting smaller enough, the structure of $\Delta(S)$ will degenerate to a basic shape like curve to a tiny line segment, sphere surface to a tiny plane, the $\Delta(S)$ of 3d objects turn to solid sphere or cube, and even for boundaries or discontinuous points, it will stay the basic structure but with some missing part.

iv: However, for fractals, things changed, no matter how smaller the area of $\Delta(S)$ is getting, it will always stay sort of fractal structure. For fractals consist of lines, even in $\Delta(S)$ which area is smaller enough, the number of vectors in $B_p \geq 1$, That's the crucial reason why the dimension of a fractal line will exceed 1 d and where dimension continuity originated from.

Symmetry and Dimension

- Major Conjectures:

i: If the basic structure and its iteration structure of a fractal are fully symmetric about the basis vectors in $\{B_p\}$, then the fractal is evenly distributed, then the dimension of fractal must be integer and:

$$d = \text{Len}(B_p),$$

otherwise:

$$d < \text{Len}(B_p).$$

ii: the dimension will be determined by the symmetry, which means there might exist strong relationship between dimension d and symmetry HS for more general cases:

$$\text{HS} = \text{SysMeas}(\text{XP}, B_p)$$

$$d \cong \text{HS}$$

The basic structure and its iteration structure will determine its measure, which will be discussed in next part of Major Details Analysis.

- Base Analysis:

i: Symmetric about the basis vectors means:

$$\text{XP}(n, b_i) = \text{XP}(n, -b_i)$$

$$\text{XP}^j(n+1, b_i) = \text{XP}^j(n+1, -b_i)$$

$$b_i \in \{B_p\}$$

There are two points here: the basic structure itself is symmetric with b_i ; and the iteration structures from last scale should be symmetrically distributed with b_i , which means for each structure iterating from last scale, there do exist a mirror or symmetric one with $b_i \in \{B_p\}$.

ii: And we're going to introduce a more general definition of basic iteration structure symmetry, Entropy symmetry:

$$\text{ES}(\text{XP}, b_i) = \text{ES}(\text{XP}, -b_i)$$

$$ES(XP_{n+1}^j, b_i) = ES(XP_{n+1}^{j'}, -b_i)$$

$$b_i \in \{B_p\}$$

First: Entropy Symmetry means the basic structure is entropy symmetric about the basis b_i .

Second: It also means the new structures which iterating from the basic structure will be entropy symmetrically distributed corresponding to the basis b_i .

iii: Strong relationship between dimension d and symmetry HS.

First, HS means the measure of the symmetry in the basic structure and its iteration structure of a fractal.

Second, the fractal's dimension d is strongly related to the symmetry, in some fully symmetric cases, the dimension:

$$d = HS,$$

and the SysMeas will be simplified to Len, that:

$$HS = SysMeas(XP, b_i) = Len(B_p).$$

Or At least the symmetry will determine the lower or upper boundary of dimension d .

Above all, that's why the author of this paper decide to use \cong to show the relationship between dimension and symmetry.

iv: Below are some examples of symmetry and dimension:

- Basic Structure and Iteration of Koch Line With Its Symmetry:

- Basic Structure and Iteration of Simple Tree Fractal With Its Symmetry:

- Basic Structure and Iteration of Grid Fractal with Its Symmetry:

- Basic Structure and Iteration of Sierpinski Fractal with Its Symmetry:

First: For Koch lines, simple tree fractal, and Sierpinski Fractal, they get two basis in B_p , $B_p = \{b_x, b_y\}$, and obviously, they stay symmetric about b_x , but non-symmetric about b_y ,

so for these fractals:

$$Len(B_p) = 2$$

$$d < Len(B_p); d < 2$$

Second: For Grid Fractal, it also gets two basis in B_p , $B_p = \{b_x, b_y\}$, and apparently, it stays symmetric both about b_x and b_y .

$$Len(B_p) = 2$$

$$d = 2$$

As below, we're going to continue analysis the details of basic structures and its iteration structures of fractals with different perspectives.

Major Details Analysis

Measure/Position/Direction/Quantity

We're going to analysis the iteration rules or patterns of fractals changing in measure, direction, position, quantity under the framework.

Measure(length, area, volume, ...).

(1) For static fractal framework:

Please refer to the equation 1.1 and 2.1, in which:

$V(s_i)$ is fixed, has nothing to do with scale (s_i).

V_j are the X-fractal basis.

For static fractal, V_j are fixed and have nothing to do with scale.

First: Let's take a look at classical static structure fractals, like simple tree fractal:

To simplify the discussion, tree fractal will start from one line and iterating with fixed rules.

Symbol Descriptions:

l_0 : the length of trunk at initial scale

l_1 : the length of branch at second scale.

...

l_n : the length of branch at n-th scale.

...

d_i : the ratio of length. Which can be either 1 or d_r , 1 means the old trunk will preserve, d_r (like 0.6) means the ratio of length of new branch to its old trunk.

$$l_1 = d * l_0; l_2 = d * l_1; l_3 = d * l_2 \dots l_n = d * l_{n-1} \dots$$

$$\rightarrow l_n = d * l_{n-1}$$

$$\rightarrow \log(l_n) = \log(d_0 * d_1 * \dots * d_n) + \log(l_0)$$

So for simple tree fractals, from the aspect of measure:

$$l_n = d_n * l_{n-1}$$

$$\log(l_n) = \sum_{i=1}^n \log(d_i) + \log(l_0)$$

- The initial element of such fractal is a line segment;
- The basic element is also a line segment.
- XP means the measure, the length.
- XF means the log.
- The X-fractal basis is $\{d_0, d_r\}$, $d_0 = 1$, d_r could be some certain ratio, both are fixed.
- $d_0 = 1$, $d_r < 1$, not only means the old trunk preserves, but also reveal that it's a mix system of normal object and strict fractal in the perspective of traditional way.
- For a simple tree fractal consist with lines in a 2d space, points about symmetry:

As n-th scale is positive finite, which means the normal object part, $B_p = \{b_x\}$. For most interior points of this normal object part, it stays symmetric with b_x , so:

$$\text{Len}(B_p) = 1, d = 1$$

But as $n \rightarrow \infty$, $B_p = \{b_x, b_y\}$ for the very top part of such simple tree which is a strict fractal, it stays symmetric with b_x , but non-symmetric with b_y , so:

$$\text{Len}(B_p) = 2, d < 2$$

(2) For static fractal framework with randomness:

We'll still discuss this fractal with simple tree fractals, but with some randomness introduced.

Please refer to the equation 1.4,2.4, in which V is fixed to scale.

Symbol Description:

rl_i means the randomness introduced to the i-th scale for length.

PS: Other symbols please refer to "For static fractal framework" and "Symbol Description" above.

$$l_n = d * rl_n * l_{n-1}$$

$$l_n = d^n * rl_1 * rl_2 * rl_3 * \dots * rl_n * l_0$$

$$rl' = l_1 * rl_2 * rl_3 * \dots * rl_n$$

So for simple static tree fractals with randomness, from the aspect of measure:

$$l_n = d * rl_n * l_{n-1}$$

$$\log(l_n) = \sum_{i=1}^n \log(d_i) + \log(l_0) + \log(rl')$$

Conclusion of static fractals with randomness:

- The randomness is rl .
- The X-fractal basis is $\{d_0, d_r\}$, $d_0 = 1$, d_r are both fixed.
- Other analysis: usually, $0 <= d * rl_i < 1$, means the tree fractal will iterate to a fixed area. Growing will converge. As $n \rightarrow \infty$ $l_n \rightarrow 0$.
- But sometimes: like banyan tree: As $d * rl_n > 1$, it's going to break the limitation of converge, I call it newborn, which means a new trunk or a new banyan tree will grow.

- Symmetric Point For such fractals:

As n-th scale is positive finite, $B_p = \{b_x\}$. For most interior part of this simple tree with randomness which is normal object part, non-strict fractal part, it stays symmetric with b_x , so:

$$\text{Len } B_p = 1, d = 1$$

But as $i \rightarrow \infty$, $B_p = \{b_x, b_y\}$ for the very top part of this fractal which is the strict standard fractal part, it stays entropy symmetric with b_x (symmetric for most evenly random cases, entropy non-symmetric for some biased random cases), but non-symmetric with b_y , so:

$$\text{Len } B_p = 2, d < 2$$

(3) For linear fractal framework:

We'll still discuss this fractal with tree fractals, but for each scale, the iteration rules are changing, $V(s_i)$ is linear to scale i.

For equations please refer to equation 1.2 and 2.2.

Symbols Description:

d_i : the i-th ratio.

$$d_i = a * i + b$$

PS: Other symbols please refer to "For static fractal framework" and "Symbol Description" above.

$$l_1 = d_1 * l_0; l_2 = d_2 * l_1; \dots l_n = d_n * l_{n-1} \dots$$

$$\rightarrow l_n = (a * n + b) * l_{n-1}$$

$$\rightarrow \log(l_n) = \sum_{i=1}^n \log(a * i + b) + \log(l_0)$$

Conclusion:

- The initial element of such fractal is a line segment;
- The basic element is also a line.
- \overline{XP} means the measure, the length.
- \overline{XF} means the log
- $\{a * i + b\}$ are the x-fractal basis, which are linear to its scale.
- About symmetry please check the contents in static fractal framework.

(4) For linear fractal with randomness framework:

We'll still discuss this fractal with tree fractals, but for each scale, the iteration rules are changing, $V(s_i)$ is linear to scale i; and also with the randomness introduced: $R(s_i)$ is the randomness introduced on the i-th scale.

For equations, please refer to 1.5,2.5.

Symbols Description:

rl_i : the i-th randomness.

$$d_i = a * i + b$$

PS: Other symbols please check above.

$$l_1 = d_1 * rl_1 * l_0; l_2 = d_2 * rl_2 * l_1; \dots l_n = d_n * rl_n * l_{n-1} \dots$$

$$\rightarrow l_n = (a * n + b) * rl_n * l_{n-1}$$

$$\rightarrow \log(l_n) = \sum_{i=1}^n \log(a * i + b) + \log(rl') + \log(l_0)$$

Conclusions:

- $\{a * i + b\}$ are the x-fractal basis.
 - rl' is the randomness introduced.
- Others please check above.

(5) For non-linear fractal framework:

Equations please check 1.31,1.32,2.31.

Symbols Description:

Extreme simple case1:

$$d_i = a * i^t + b$$

Simple general cases, the \overline{XP}_i will only be determined by \overline{XP}_{i-1} :

$$d_i = \text{NFV}(i, a, b, \dots)$$

More general cases: for the \overline{XP}_i will be determined by several last scales like $\overline{XP}_{j_0}, \overline{XP}_{j_1} \dots$:

$$d_i = \{\text{NFV}(i_0, a, b, \dots), \text{NFV}(i_1, a, b, \dots), \text{NFV}(i_2, a, b, \dots), \dots\}$$

PS: Other symbols please refer to "For static fractal framework" and "Symbol Description" above.

Conclusions:

- $\{\{\text{NFV}(i_0, a, b, \dots), \text{NFV}(i_1, a, b, \dots), \text{NFV}(i_2, a, b, \dots), \dots\}\}$ are the x-fractal basis
- Others please check above.

(6) For non-linear fractal with randomness framework:

Equations please check 1.61,1.62.

Symbols Description:

r_i : the i-th randomness.

$d_i = \{NFV(i0, a, b, \dots), NFV(i1, a, b, \dots), NFV(i2, a, b, \dots), \dots\}$

PS: Other symbols please refer to "For static fractal with randomness framework" and "Symbol Description" above.

Conclusions:

- $\{NFV(i0, a, b, \dots), NFV(i1, a, b, \dots), NFV(i2, a, b, \dots), \dots\}$ are the x-fractal basis
- r_i is the randomness introduced.
- Others please check above.

Direction/Position/Quantity

(1) For static fractal framework:

Please refer to the equation 1.1 and 2.1. To simplify the discussion, we'll still discuss it with simple tree fractals.

For Direction:

Symbol Description:

A_0 : the direction of trunk at initial scale

A_1 : the direction of branch at second scale.

...

A_n : the direction of branch at n-th scale.

...

M : means the rotation matrix from vector trunk to branch.

$M \in \{E, M_{left}, M_{right}\}$

$A_1 = M_1 * A_0; A_2 = M_2 * A_1; A_3 = M_3 * A_2 \dots A_n = M_n * A_{n-1} \dots$

$\rightarrow A_n = M_n * A_{n-1}$

$\rightarrow A_n = M_n * M_{n-1} * \dots * M_2 * M_1 * A_0$

$\rightarrow \log(|\det(A_n * A_0^T)|) = \sum_{j=1}^n \log(|\det(M_j)|)$

$\rightarrow XF(A_n * A_0^T) = \sum_{j=1}^n XF(M_j) + XF(A_0 * A_0^T)$

Conclusions For direction:

- $M_j \in \{E, M_{left}, M_{right}\}$, M_j has nothing to do with scale j , and is fixed for certain direction.
- E, M_{left}, M_{right} are the x-fractal basis.

For Position:

Symbol Description:

P_i means the position of i-th scale.

Vert0, Vert1 means the vertices of each line segment.

$P_i = \{Vert0_{i-1}, Vert1_{i-1}, Vert1_{i-1}\}$

Conclusions For Position:

- X-fractal basis: $\{V_i\} = \{E, M1, M2\}$

Conclusions For Quantity:

- X-fractal basis: 3.

Conclusion for symmetry and its continuity in dimension:

- For most normal object part of the simple tree, $B_p = \{b_x\}$, the measure, direction, position, quantity stay symmetric with b_x , so:
 $Len(B_p) = 1, d = 1$
- For strict fractal part (the very top part of simple tree fractal), $B_p = \{b_x, b_y\}$, they stay symmetric with b_x , but non-symmetric with b_y :
 $Len(B_p) = 2, d < 2$

(2) For static fractals with randomness framework :

Please refer to the equation 1.1 and 2.1. To simplify the discussion, we'll still discuss it with simple tree fractals, but introduce randomness to each scale.

Symbol Description:

rM_n means the n-th scale randomness introduced to directions.

$A_1 = M_1 * rM_1 * A_0; A_2 = M_2 * rM_2 * A_1; A_3 = M_3 * rM_3 * A_2 \dots A_n = M_n * rM_n * A_{n-1} \dots$

$\rightarrow A_n = M_n * rM_n * A_{n-1}$

$\rightarrow A_n = M_n * rM_n * M_{n-1} * rM_{n-1} * \dots * M_2 * rM_2 * M_1 * rM_1 * A_0$

$\rightarrow \log(|\det(A_n * A_0^T)|) = \sum_{j=1}^n \log(|\det(M_j)|) + \sum_j j = 1^i \log(|\det(rM_j)|) + \log(|\det(A_0 * A_0^T)|)$

$\rightarrow XF(A_n * A_0^T) = \sum_{j=1}^n XF(M_j) + rM' + XF(A_0 * A_0^T)$

rM' is the randomness introduced for direction.

The quantity basis is 3. If randomness rq introduced, then $q_n = \text{Int}(3 * rq) * q_{n-1}$, $\text{Int}(3 * rq)$ could be 1,2,3 or other number.

Conclusions:

- For direction: $\{E, M_{left}, M_{right}\}$ are the x-fractal basis.
- For position: $\{E, M1, M2\}$ are the x-fractal basis.
- For quantity: 3 is the x-fractal basis.
- For randomness: we could introduce randomness to direction like rM' , position like rP , quantity for rq .
- For symmetry and its continuity in dimension:

For the part which scale n stay positive finite, $B_p = \{b_x\}$, they stay symmetric with b_x , so:

$$\text{Len}(B_p) = 1, d = 1$$

For the very top of simple tree fractal, when $n \rightarrow \infty$, $B_p = \{b_x, b_y\}$, they stay entropy symmetric with b_x for most evenly random cases, but non-symmetric with b_y :

$$\text{Len}(B_p) = 2, d < 2$$

(3) For Linear structure fractal framework:

Please refer to the equation 1.2 and 2.2. To simplify the discussion, we'll still discuss it with tree fractals. In which x-fractal basis V_j are linear to scale j .

Symbol Descriptions:

$$A_1 = M_1 * A_0; A_2 = M_2 * A_1; A_3 = M_3 * A_2 \dots A_n = M_n * A_{n-1} \dots$$

$$\rightarrow A_n = M_n * A_{n-1}$$

$$\rightarrow \log(|\det(A_n * A_0^T)|) = \sum_{j=1}^n \log(|\det(M_j)|)$$

For rotation:

$$M_j \in \{E, Ml_j, Mr_j\}$$

$$Ml_j = Ml(\theta_j) = Ml(\theta_{al} * j + \theta_{bl}) = Ml(\theta_{al})^j * Ml(\theta_{bl})$$

$$Mr_j = Mr(\theta_j) = Mr(\theta_{ar} * j + \theta_{br}) = Mr(\theta_{ar})^j * Mr(\theta_{br})$$

$$\text{XF}(Ml_j) = j * \text{XF}(Ml(\theta_{al})) + \text{XF}(Ml(\theta_{bl}))$$

$$\text{XF}(Mr_j) = j * \text{XF}(Mr(\theta_{ar})) + \text{XF}(Mr(\theta_{br}))$$

XF could be Matrix Logarithm and logarithm of determinant

Ml, Mr , both have linear relationship with j from the perspective of rotation angle, and operation of Matrix Logarithm and logarithm of determinant.

Conclusions:

- For Direction: $\{E, Ml_j, Mr_j\}$ are the x-fractal basis of this framework. In which they hold linear relationship with j .
- For Position: the x-fractal basis are $\{E, M1, M2\}$, and of course, we could also introduce linear relationship to the varying of position.
- For Quantity: the x-fractal basis is 3.
- Symmetry and continuity of dimension please refer to static structure fractal.

(4) Linear structure with random fractals:

Please refer to the equation 1.5 and 2.5. To simplify the discussion, we'll still discuss it with tree fractals. In which x-fractal basis V_j are linear to scale j , and randomness introduced.

Symbol Descriptions And Analysis:

V_j is linear to scale j .

rM_i is the randomness introduced on i -th scale.

$$A_1 = M_1 * rM_1 * A_0; A_2 = M_2 * rM_2 * A_1; A_3 = M_3 * rM_3 * A_2 \dots A_n = M_n * rM_n * A_{n-1} \dots$$

$$\rightarrow A_n = M_n * rM_i * A_{n-1}$$

$$\rightarrow \log(|\det(A_n * A_0^T)|) = \sum_{j=1}^i \log(|\det(M_j)|) + \sum_{j=1}^n \log(|\det(rM_j)|) + \log(|\det(A_0 * A_0^T)|)$$

Conclusions:

- $\{E, Ml_j, Mr_j\}$ are the x-fractal basis of this framework.
- rM_j are the randomness introduced.
- Symmetry and continuity of dimension please refer to static structure with random fractal.

(5) For non-linear fractal framework:

Equations please refer to 1.31,1.32,2.31.

For simple cases, in which direction, position, quantity only determined by last scale:

Symbol Descriptions And Analysis:

$$A_n = M_n * A_{n-1}$$

$$M_n = \text{NFR}(n, C_0, C_1 \dots)$$

$$M_n \in \{E, Ml_j, Mr_j\}$$

A_n means n th scale direction.

M_n means n th scale direction changing from last scale.

NFR means non-linear function, M_n holds non-linear relationship to n th scale.

Conclusions:

- For Direction: $\{E, Ml_j, Mr_j\}$ are the x-fractal basis of this framework. In which they hold non-linear relationship with j .

- For Position: the non-linear x-fractal basis are $\{E, M1_j, M2_j\}$, non-linear to j.
- For Quantity: the non-linear x-fractal basis $\{q_j\}$, q_j is non-linear to j.
- If in any one of these aspects (measure/direction/position/quantity), the changing pattern stays non-linear to scale, others stay static or linear, then it's a non-linear fractal framework.
- Symmetry and continuity of dimension please refer to Linear structure fractal

For complicated cases, in which direction, position, quantity will be determined by several scales or several patterns:

Example For directions:

$$A_n = \text{NFunc}(M_{n0} * A_{j0}, M_{n1} * A_{j1}, \dots)$$

$$M_j \in \{\{E, Ml_{j0}, Mr_{j0}, Ml_{j1}, Mr_{j1}, Ml_{j2}, Mr_{j2}, \dots\}\}$$

Conclusions:

- For Direction: $\{\{E, Ml_{j0}, Mr_{j0}, Ml_{j1}, Mr_{j1}, Ml_{j2}, Mr_{j2}, \dots\}\}$ are the x-fractal basis of this framework. In which they hold non-linear relationship with j.
- For Position: the non-linear x-fractal basis are $\{\{E, M1_{j0}, M2_{j0}, M1_{j1}, M2_{j1}, \dots\}\}$, non-linear to j.
- For Quantity: the non-linear x-fractal basis $\{\{q_{j0}, q_{j1}, q_{j2}, \dots\}\}$, q_{j} is non-linear to j.

(6) For non-linear fractal with randomness framework:

Equations please refer to 1.61,1.62.

For simple cases, in which direction, position, quantity only determined by last scale:

Symbol Descriptions And Analysis:

$$A_n = M_n * rM_n * A_{n-1}$$

$$M_n = \text{NFR}(n, C_0, C_1..)$$

$$M_n \in \{E, Ml_j, Mr_j\}$$

rM_n means the randomness introduced for nth scale.

Other symbol descriptions and their explanations please check simple cases in non-linear fractal framework.

Conclusions:

- For Direction: $\{E, Ml_j, Mr_j\}$ are the x-fractal basis of this framework. In which they hold non-linear relationship with j.
- Symmetry: rM_n means randomness introduced, so we'll use entropy symmetry to measure it, once the randomness is evenly distributed, it's entropy symmetric for b_x .

When n stays positive finite:

$$B_p = \{b_x\} \text{Len}(B_p) = 1$$

$$ES(XP_n, b_x) = ES(XP_n, -b_x)$$

$$d = 1$$

When n goes ∞ :

$$B_p = \{b_x, b_y\} \text{Len}(B_p) = 2$$

$$ES(XP_n, b_x) = ES(XP_n, -b_x)$$

$$ES(XP_n, b_y) \neq ES(XP_n, -b_y)$$

$$d < 2$$

- Other conclusions please check simple cases for the non-linear fractal framework.

For complicated cases, in which direction, position, quantity will be determined by several scales or several patterns:

$$A_n = \text{NFunc}(rM_n, M_{n0} * A_{j0}, M_{n1} * A_{j1}, \dots)$$

$$M_j \in \{\{E, Ml_{j0}, Mr_{j0}, Ml_{j1}, Mr_{j1}, Ml_{j2}, Mr_{j2}, \dots\}\}$$

Conclusions:

- For Direction: $\{\{E, Ml_{j0}, Mr_{j0}, Ml_{j1}, Mr_{j1}, Ml_{j2}, Mr_{j2}, \dots\}\}$ are the x-fractal basis of this framework. In which Ml, Mr hold non-linear relationship with j.
- Symmetry please refer to the symmetry in conclusions of simple cases.
- Other conclusions please check the conclusions for non-linear fractal framework.

Other classic fractals Analysis:

Koch curve

(1) Initial element:

a straight line segment.

The position of this segment will be $\{vert0, vert1\}$

(2) basic element:

a straight line segment.

(3) Measure(length):

Its measure on new scale will be chosen from:

$$l_i = \{1/3 * l_{i-1}, 1/3 * l_{i-1}, 1/3 * l_{i-1}, 1/3 * l_{i-1}\}$$

X-fractal basis: $V = \{1/3\}$

(4) Direction:

Its direction on new scale will be chosen from:

$$\{E, M(60^\circ), M(120^\circ), E\}$$

So The X-fractal basis: $\{V_i\} = \{E, M(60^\circ), M(120^\circ)\}$

(5) Position:

Its position on new scale will be chosen from:

$$P_i = \{vert0_{i-1}, 1/3 * vert1_{i-1} + 2/3 * vert0_{i-1}, 2/3 * vert1_{i-1} + 1/3 * vert0_{i-1}\}$$

$$P_i = \{P_{i-1}, P_{i-1} + 1/3 * l_{i-1} * A_{i-1}, P_{i-1} + 2/3 * l_{i-1} * A_{2i-1}, P_{i-1} + l_{i-1} * A_{i-1}\}$$

X-fractal basis: $\{V_i\} = \{E, M1, M2\}$

(6) Quantity:

X-fractal basis: 4.

(7) Symmetry and continuity of dimension:

$B_p = \{b_x, b_y\}$, it stays symmetric with b_x , but non-symmetric with b_y so:

$$\text{Len}(B_p) = 2, d < 2$$

Sierpinski fractal

(1) Initial element:

A triangle constructed with three straight line segments

The position of three vertices of triangle will be: $\{vert0, vert1, vert2\}$

(2) Basic element:

A triangle

(3) Measure(length):

Its measure on new scale will be chosen from:

$$l_i = \{1/2 * l_{i-1}, 1/2 * l_{i-1}, 1/2 * l_{i-1}\}$$

So its X-fractal basis: $V = \{1/2\}$

(4) Direction:

Its direction on new scale will be chosen from:

$$\{E, E, E\}$$

So The X-fractal basis: $\{E\}$

(5) Position:

Its position on new scale will be chosen from:

$$P_i = \{vert0_{i-1}, 1/2 * vert0_{i-1} + 1/2 * vert1_{i-1}, 1/2 * vert0_{i-1} + 1/2 * vert2_{i-1}\}$$

So the X-fractal basis: $\{E, M1, M2\}$

(6) Quantity:

X-fractal basis: 3.

(7) Symmetry:

$B_p = \{b_x, b_y\}$, it stays symmetric with b_x , but non-symmetric with b_y so:

$$\text{Len}(B_p) = 2, d < 2$$

Koch snowflake

(1) Initial element:

Three line segments which construct an equilateral triangle.

The position of this segment will be $\{vert0, vert1, vert2\}$.

(2) Basic element:

A line segment.

(3) Measure(length):

Its measure on new scale will be chosen from:

$$l_i = \{1/3 * l_{i-1}, 1/3 * l_{i-1}, 1/3 * l_{i-1}, \dots, 1/3 * l_{i-1}\}, \text{ repeat time} = 3.$$

X-fractal basis: $V = \{1/3\}$

(4) Direction:

Its direction on new scale will be chosen from:

$$\{E, M(60^\circ), M(120^\circ), \dots, E\}, \text{ repeat time} = 3$$

So The X-fractal basis: $\{V_i\} = \{E, M(60^\circ), M(120^\circ)\}$

(5) Position:

Its position on new scale will be chosen from:

For line($vert0_{i-1}, vert1_{i-1}$):

$$P_i = \{vert0_{i-1}, 1/3 * vert1_{i-1} + 2/3 * vert0_{i-1}, 2/3 * vert1_{i-1} + 1/3 * vert0_{i-1}\}$$

For line($vert0_{i-1}, vert2_{i-1}$):

$$P_i = \{vert0_{i-1}, 1/3 * vert2_{i-1} + 2/3 * vert0_{i-1}, 2/3 * vert2_{i-1} + 1/3 * vert0_{i-1}\}$$

For line($vert1_{i-1}, vert2_{i-1}$):

$$P_i = \{vert1_{i-1}, 1/3 * vert2_{i-1} + 2/3 * vert1_{i-1}, 2/3 * vert2_{i-1} + 1/3 * vert1_{i-1}\}$$

X-fractal basis: $\{V_i\} = \{E, M1, M2\}$

(6) Quantity:

X-fractal basis: 4.

(7) Symmetry and continuity of dimension:

i: $B_p = \{b_x, b_y\}$, it stays symmetric with b_x , but non-symmetric with b_y so:

$$\text{Len}(B_p) = 2, d < 2$$

ii: Actually Koch snowflake is a bit special about symmetry, because the Whole shape stays perfectly symmetric. But As what we already discussed in chapter Key Points of Core Framework, the symmetry what we discussed and connected to dimension is the symmetry of basic structure(element) and the symmetric distributions of structures iterating from last scale for each $\Delta(S)$.

Simple 2D Cloud fractals

(1) Initial basic element:

circle.

The center coordinates of circle could be (0,0), the radius could be r. All of these will be described under polar coordinates.

(2) Basic element:

sphere.

(3) Measure(area):

$ratio_r = \phi' \approx 0.6180339887$, usually the golden ratio conjugate.

$$Area_i = \pi * r_i^2$$

$$r_i = ratio_r * r_{i-1}$$

$$Area_i = ratio_r^2 * Area_{i-1}$$

Its measure on new scale will be chosen from:

$$\{1, d\}$$

So the x-fractal basis will be $\{1, d\}$

(4) Direction:

Its direction on new scale will be chosen from:

$$\{E\}$$

So The X-fractal basis: $V = \{E\}$

(5) Position:

$$\text{helix: } h = a * \theta$$

For the center coordinates:

$$P_0 = (0, 0), P_1 = (a * \Delta\theta, \Delta\theta), P_2 = (a * 2 * \Delta\theta, 2 * \Delta\theta) \dots$$

$$P_n = P_{n-1} + (a * \Delta\theta, \Delta\theta)$$

$$P_n = (a * n * \Delta\theta, n * \Delta\theta)$$

So The X-fractal basis: $V = \{M1\}$

(6) Quantity:

X-fractal basis: 2.

Julia set for Douady's rabbit

(1) Initial basic element:

An rugby ball shape but with a bit sharp point ends.

(2) Basic element:

An rugby ball shape but with a bit sharp point ends.

(3) X-fractal basis:

X-fractal basis for quantity: C , a positive finite number.

X-fractal basis for measure: $\{r_1, r_2, r_3, r_4, \dots, r_c\}$ with limited count r_j .

So do for Direction, position, in which they repeat the structure of Douady's rabbit on each scale with varying based on x-fractal basis.

Not symmetric, $\text{Len}(B_p) = 2 d < 2$

Brownian motion trajectory

(1) Initial basic element:

Randomly distributed line segments in several tiny grids.

(2) Basic element:

Randomly distributed line segments in a tiny grid.

(3) X-fractal basis:

Based on equation of Brownian motion trajectory:

$$B(at) \propto \sqrt{a}B(t) \text{ [8]}$$

X-fractal basis for measure:

$$\{C1 * \sqrt{\delta(t)}\}$$

Which means it's going to travel at the distance of r:

$$r = C1 * \sqrt{\delta(t)}$$

in $\delta(t)$, inversely:

$$\delta(t) \propto r^2$$

X-fractal basis for quantity: 4. Which means if it travels r_0 length of grid in t_0 , then it will take $4 * t_0$ to travel 4 grids.

(4) Symmetry:

Above all, and according to the property of neighborhood-recurrent [9], we can conclude that the basic structure and its iteration structure of Brownian motion trajectory is entropy symmetric, that it will scatter probability evenly in one tiny grid within time of t_0 , then it will scatter evenly in 2 tiny grids within time of $4 * t_0$.

$$B_p = \{b_x, b_y\}$$

$$\text{Len}(B_p) = 2$$

$$ES(XP, b_x) = ES(XP, -b_x)$$

$$ES(XP, b_y) = ES(XP, -b_y)$$

$$d = 2$$

Application

- i: We could analyze a fractal with x-fractal basis to check the details of iterating for direction, position, measure, and its quantity.
- ii: Its intuitive dimension can be concluded from the angle of entropy symmetry for some complicated cases like Brownian motion trajectory, turbulence.

Conclusion

This paper provides a new fractal classification framework and a new mathematic model from different perspectives of measure, direction, position, quantity to analysis fractals.

We also try to reveal the nature of dimension and its dimension continuity, and propose conjectures about fractals: that the symmetry of basic structure and its iteration structure will determine the fractals' dimension. We also introduce a more general way to define the structure symmetry, entropy symmetry.

Furthermore, we define the x-fractal basis based on different perspectives which will determine the fractals' structure and their measure and give a detail mathematic explanation based on examples of tree fractals, Koch curve, snowflake, Sierpinski fractals and so on.

Future work and its limits

i: Will randomness down the pattern (like linear structure ...), when it's strong enough? Or because we don't find the true pattern deep down, so we recognize it as some randomness?

ii: Conjecture the strong relationship between the dimension and its symmetry in basic structure and its iteration structure, has not fully discussed and logically proved. Equations as below:

$$HS = \text{SymMeas}(XP, B_p)$$

$$d \cong HS.$$

And Maybe there only exist strong relationship between symmetry and dimension lower or upper boundary:

$$\text{UpperOrLowerBound}(d) = HS.$$

iii: Views about Symmetry is not that clear, and fully supported, especially in Koch Snow Flake.

iv: Randomness evenly, such concept which connected to entropy symmetry and dimension are not fully discussed and proved.

v: The X-fractal basis and the basic structure might have some deep and profound connection with dimension and its measure, which need to expand and dig a bit more.

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